

**THE MEDIATING EFFECT OF PROFESSIONAL COMMITMENT IN THE
RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN JOB SATISFACTION AND WORKPLACE
SPIRITUALITY AMONG PUBLIC SCHOOL TEACHERS**

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The Mediating Effect of Professional Commitment in the Relationship between Job Satisfaction and Workplace Spirituality among Public School Teachers

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Abstract

The main thrust of the study was to find out the mediating effect of professional commitment on the relationship between job satisfaction and workplace spirituality among 269 public school teachers in Alabel 3 District of Sarangani Division. This study employed a non-experimental quantitative design utilizing the descriptive correlation technique. The statistical tools used were, mean Pearson r and Path Analysis. Based on the study results, the level of professional commitment and job satisfaction were rated high by the respondents while, they most observed all the time regarding workplace spirituality. Using Pearson r, the results revealed a significant relationship between job satisfaction and workplace spirituality, job satisfaction and professional commitment, and professional commitment and workplace spirituality. The study's findings, based on the path analysis, indicated that professional commitment partially mediates job satisfaction, however, workplace spirituality does not. As a result, the study's findings revealed that professional commitment, a mediating variable, impacted public school teachers' job satisfaction. In terms of pay and benefits, job security, recognition, career development, engagement, and respect, fostering professional dedication can have a favorable impact on job satisfaction.

Keywords: *educational management, professional commitment, job satisfaction, workplace spirituality*

Introduction

Workplace spirituality has received a lot of attention lately. It refers to enhancing the standard of the workplace environment by introducing spiritual activities and beliefs. According to research, workplace spirituality can enhance workers' feeling of purpose and job satisfaction, among other good outcomes. Additionally, it may increase workers' sense of purpose at work and improve their general well-being (Burack et al., 2022).

While incorporating spiritual practices in the workplace may not always be easy, it is vital to recognize that doing so may have benefits such as improved job satisfaction and a sense of purpose among employees. Organizations must find a way to accommodate individual views and interests while encouraging spirituality. Furthermore, it is critical to guarantee that workplace spirituality is inclusive and does not discriminate against employees based on their spiritual or religious convictions. Previous research has identified various aspects of spirituality in the workplace. Still, more qualitative studies, cross-cultural investigations, and analyses of the connections between workplace spirituality and trust, mindset, innovative behavior, and sustainable behavior are needed (Singh et al., 2022).

On the other hand, the importance of workplace spirituality can help create a more positive and inclusive workplace culture. When employees feel that they are part of an organization that values their spiritual beliefs and allows them to bring their whole selves to work, they are more likely to feel accepted and valued. Workplace spirituality imbues previous work practices of interconnectedness and trust among individuals involved in a specific work process. This, in turn, triggers cooperative feelings and results in an overall organizational culture motivated by positive responses, unanimity, and harmony among the individuals. Consequently, this raises the individuals' collective performance, which helps the organization (Rehman et al., 2023).

However, modern businesses must deal with employee-related issues like stress-related illnesses, burnout, absenteeism, violence, and corruption. These workplace issues are typical in businesses without a spiritual component (Ashfaq & Irum, 2020). Many believe that for 21st-century organizations to exist, leaders and staff must draw on spiritual resources. Employees will also become more productive, creative, and fulfilled if they can contribute their physical, intellectual, emotional, and spiritual qualities to work (Barr & Nathenson, 2022).

In the Philippines, Public school teachers face challenges that affect their job satisfaction and professional commitment, such as low pay, inadequate resources, high workload, lack of support and recognition, and challenging working conditions. Teachers have also faced several challenges related to professional commitment, job satisfaction, and workplace spirituality. These include a lack of resources and support, a high workload and long working hours, cultural differences and language barriers, and workplace politics and favoritism. Integrating workplace spirituality can enhance job satisfaction and reduce stress and burnout. (Garcia & Juevesa, 2020).

Research Objectives

Specifically, this research study sought to answer the following questions:

1. To describe the level of job satisfaction in terms of:
 - 1.1. pay and benefit;
 - 1.2. job security;

- 1.3. recognition;
- 1.4. career development, and
- 1.5. engagement; and
- 1.6. respect.
2. To ascertain the extent of workplace spirituality of public-school teachers in terms of:
 - 2.1. compassion;
 - 2.2. mindfulness;
 - 2.3. meaningful work;
 - 2.4. transcendence.
3. To measure the level of professional commitment in terms of:
 - 3.1. continuance professional commitment;
 - 3.2. affective professional commitment; and
 - 3.3. normative professional commitment.
4. To acknowledge the respondent's reflections about teaching as their present career in terms of:
 - 4.1. job satisfaction and workplace spirituality;
 - 4.2. job satisfaction and professional commitment; and
 - 4.3. professional commitment and workplace spirituality.
5. To determine the significant mediation of professional commitment on job satisfaction and workplace spirituality.

Methodology

This study employed the quantitative non-experimental approach, using a correlation technique to measure the association between passion and commitment. Descriptive non-experimental correlational design controlled the degree to which one variable relates to another or more variables (Goertzen et al., 2023). In this study, the correlation method is the best strategy to achieve this study's goals and find out whether the hypothesis is accepted. H_0 is born, and H_a is accepted if the significance value exceeds 0.5. Hypothesis testing determines whether the correlations are strong or weak (Creswell, 2021).

Additionally, since this is a fact-finding study, the researcher may examine the characteristics, behaviors, and experiences of the study participants (Wang et al., 2020). The study was descriptive since it assessed the levels of professional commitment, job satisfaction, and workplace spirituality among public school teachers in Sarangani Province, Region XII. This study used a survey questionnaire to collect primary data and examined the association between characteristics, including workplace spirituality, job happiness, and professional dedication. As a result, the study was correlational.

The study was conducted in nine (9) different schools in the Alabel 3 District, Division of Sarangani. It was conducted from January to February 2023 among Public School Teachers in Alabel 3 District. There were nine (9) public schools in Alabel 3 District where the study was conducted.

Alabel is the first-class and capital municipality of the province of Sarangani. It is 166 radial kilometers South of Davao City and 15 radial kilometers East of General Santos City. It can be reached by taking a thirty-minute ride on any public transport vehicle from General Santos City airport or catching a public jeepney or multi-cab going to Poblacion and other neighboring barangays of Alabel.

In addition, Alabel is strategically located on the eastern side of the Province of Sarangani, bounded on the North by the Municipality of Malungon, on the South and East by the Municipality of Malapatan, and on the west by the City of General Santos and Sarangani Bay. Also, Alabel was divided into four school districts: Alabel 1 District, Alabel 2 District, Alabel 3 District, and Alabel 4 District. Alabel 3 District is composed of 9 schools: Francisco Laiz Central Elementary School, Upper Alabel Elementary School, Vicente Fuentes Elementary School, Spring Integrated School, Paraiso Integrated School, Nop Elementary School, Alabel Science High School, Alabel National High School, and Sarangani Sports Academy.

The study's respondents were 269 public school teachers from 9 different schools in the municipality of Alabel, Alabel 3 District, Division of Sarangani, for the school year 2022-2023. A stratified random sampling approach with proportionate allocation was employed to ensure that every participant had an equal opportunity to be included in the study and to acquire a sample frame of the distribution of responses. A stratified sampling design was used to determine the appropriate number of samples selected at random (Alam et al., 2019).

Inclusion criteria for respondents in this study were established to ensure the relevance and sustainability of the sample. Firstly, public school teachers from diverse backgrounds were included to capture various perspectives. Secondly, respondents needed to have a maximum of three years of teaching experience to ensure adequate professional expertise. Thirdly, individuals with varying levels of job satisfaction, as assessed by a validated instrument, were included to explore the relationship between workplace spirituality. Lastly, respondents were required to have experience in their teaching environment to investigate the mediating effect of professional commitment on the relationship above.

Exclusion criteria were implemented to preserve the study's integrity and focus. Firstly, private school teachers were excluded as the

research specifically targeted public school teachers' contexts. Secondly, teachers with less than three years of experience were excluded to ensure adequate professional competence and familiarity with the teaching environment. Lastly, respondents with no prior knowledge or limited interaction with their teaching environment were excluded as the study aimed to examine the mediating effect of professional commitment in the relationship between job satisfaction and workplace spirituality among public school teachers.

Withdrawal criteria addressed potential ethical concerns and protected the respondents' well-being. Respondents had the right to withdraw from the study at any stage without providing a reason. Additionally, respondents who experienced any distress or discomfort during the data collection process were allowed to cancel without consequence. Strict confidentiality measures were employed to ensure that participants' identities and responses were kept anonymous, further promoting safety and privacy throughout the study.

Experts in questionnaire building evaluated three sets of questions from various writers. The experts' comments were taken correctly and incorporated into the instrument's finalization. The contents of the adopted standardized questionnaire are reliable because the author has already tested and demonstrated them. Additionally, the questionnaire underwent modification to classify questions. The questionnaires were created in very detailed form with the assistance of proficient validators to give convenience and satisfaction to the respondents in responding to every concern, as well as comprehension of the purpose of the investigation.

Validity and Reliability of the Questionnaire

The questionnaire for job satisfaction was modified to fit into the study and was subjected to validation by experts.

In evaluating the job satisfaction of teachers, the five orderable gradations with their respective range of means and descriptions were used as follows:

Rating Scale	Descriptive Equivalent	Interpretation
4.2-5.0	Strongly Agree	The level of job satisfaction is very high.
3.4-4.1	Agree	The level of job satisfaction is high.
2.6-3.3	Moderately Agree	The level of job satisfaction is fairly high.
1.8-2.5	Disagree	The level of job satisfaction is low.
1.0-1.7	Strong Disagree	The level of job satisfaction is very low.

Further, the questionnaire for workplace spirituality was adapted from the study entitled *Workplace Spirituality, Meditation, and Work Performance*, Journal of Management, Spirituality & Religion by Shrestha et al. (2023). It was modified to fit the study and subjected to expert validation. The questionnaire for workplace spirituality had the following indicators: compassion, meaningful work, transcendence, and mindfulness.

.In evaluating the workplace spirituality of teachers, the five orderable gradations with their respective range of means and descriptions were used as follows:

Rating Scale	Descriptive Equivalent	Interpretation
3.4-4.0	Always	The extent of workplace spirituality is extensively observed all the time.
2.6-3.3	Often	The extent of workplace spirituality is extensive most of the time.
1.8-2.5	Sometimes	The extent of workplace spirituality is a bit observed.
1.0-1.7	Never	The extent of workplace spirituality is not at all observed.

Moreover, the questionnaire for professional commitment was adapted from Smith and Hall (2018). It was modified to fit into the study and validated by the experts. The questionnaire had the following indicators: affective professional commitment, continuance professional commitment, and normative professional commitment.

The research adviser received the initial draft of the research instrument and was asked for feedback, ideas, and recommendations on improving its presentation and including the necessary modifications. The final copies were submitted to the experts for refinement. The final revision incorporated the corrections, comments, and suggestions the expert validators gave before gathering data. The consolidated expert results obtained an average weighted mean of 5.0, a verbal Very High description. Therefore, the instrument was in excellent use.

The necessary data was gathered using a systematic procedure. After developing a research questionnaire, the researcher sought validation from experts in the field to ensure its accuracy and effectiveness. Once the validation process was completed and the necessary revisions were made, the researcher submitted an application letter outlining the study protocol to the Ethics and Review Committee. Following a thorough application review, the committee approved the research to proceed. With the approval in hand, the researcher then sent a letter to the Dean of the Graduate School, notifying them of the study and seeking any additional guidance or support as needed. Subsequently, the researcher requested authorization to conduct the study in writing from the Superintendent of the

School Division of the Department of Education in Sarangani Division. Additionally, the researcher submitted a second letter to the Alabel-3 district supervisor of the many schools that were the subject of this study, requesting permission to conduct the survey among the teachers at each school and then use the Informed Consent Form to explain the findings. After approval, the public school instructors were given survey questionnaires.

One week following the distribution, the researcher physically collected the surveys to give the respondents ample opportunity to reply. All of the issued surveys were collected in total. After that, the completed results were verified and totaled. After the data's totalization, the findings were examined and evaluated in light of the study's objectives.

Results and Discussion

The Level of Professional Commitment

Table 1 shows the level of professional commitment in terms of affective, continuance, and normative professional commitment.

Data revealed a very high level of professional commitment, with a general weighted mean of 4.3, which indicates a strong agreement.

Ineffective professional commitment: The level of professional commitment was very high, with a total mean score of 4.3, which indicated that they strongly agreed that they were proud, felt very loyal, and cared about the fate of their profession. However, some were extremely glad that they chose their profession over other careers and felt very loyal to it.

In continuance professional commitment, the level of professional commitment was very high, with a total mean score of 4.4 indicating strongly agreed; they found values and the profession's values were very similar, and the profession inspired them the very best in the way of job performance. To help their profession be valued, the instructors were prepared to work harder than what is often anticipated.

The level of normative professional commitment was very high, as shown in the mean of 4.6, which strongly implies that teachers needed more to gain in sticking with the profession's policies and accepting almost any job assignment to keep working in this profession. It would take little change in present circumstances to change professions.

The level of professional commitment was very high regarding continuance, affective professional commitment, and normative professional commitment. Teachers have a very high level of investment and personal commitment to their careers, as leaving the profession would result in significant disruption, waste of past investment, and personal sacrifice. This practical and emotional commitment to their profession has implications for retention and talent management.

This presumption was supported by the research of Mokhtar et al. (2023), which found that instructors were more likely to continue in the field if they felt comfortable in their roles, received more compensation, and had less workload. Furthermore, teachers' decisions to stay in the field are influenced mainly by how satisfied they are with their jobs; thus, raising their self-efficacy may be a helpful strategy for encouraging their dedication.

Table 1. *The Level of Professional Commitment*

Indicators	SD	Mean	Description	Interpretation
Affective	0.622	4.3	Strongly Agree	Very High
Continuance	0.265	4.4	Strongly Agree	Very High
Normative	0.100	4.6	Strongly Agree	Very High
Overall	0.329	4.3	Strongly Agree	Very High

The Level of Job Satisfaction

Table 2 shows job satisfaction regarding pay and benefits, job security, recognition, career development, engagement, and respect. Mean was utilized to treat the gathered data.

Data revealed that job satisfaction was high, with a weighted mean of 3.7, indicating agreement.

The level of job satisfaction was high in terms of pay and benefits, as shown in the mean of 3.5, which indicates that teachers were satisfied with their compensation, ability to meet their basic needs, and the benefits and privileges provided by their Department of Education.

The mean of 3.9 reflects high job security satisfaction, indicating that teachers believe in the importance of job security and their entitlement to tenure as long as they fulfill their responsibilities effectively. They also believe termination should only occur for valid reasons and through a fair process. Additionally, the author mentions receiving appropriate rewards and bonuses.

In recognition, the level of job satisfaction was high, as shown in the mean of 3.8. It was agreed that teachers described feeling appreciated and acknowledged for their skills and contributions in their work environment. They also expressed their belief that they had opportunities to utilize their talents and be recognized for their accomplishments within their school or division.

Regarding career development, the level of job satisfaction was high, as shown in the mean of 3.7, which indicates that the teachers

discussed their experience with regular work evaluations and their willingness to participate in tasks and activities held within their school. They also expressed their commitment to working hard and meeting the requirements during team-building exercises to complete tasks successfully.

In terms of engagement, the level of job satisfaction was high, as shown in the mean of 3.7, implicating agreement that the teachers described their experience of being given independence and control in completing assigned tasks, feeling engaged in meaningful work within their school or organization, and being involved in decision-making processes that impacted their community.

Regarding respect, the instructors' level of work satisfaction was high, as seen by the mean score of 3.7, indicating that they believed in treating people with dignity and respect, regardless of their skills or contributions. They also emphasized the importance of actively listening and understanding others' perspectives and concerns. Finally, the author believed in treating others with the same level of respect and kindness that they would like to receive.

Table 2. The Level of Job Satisfaction

Indicators	SD	Mean	Description	Interpretation
Pay and Benefits	0.058	3.5	Agree	High
Job Security	0.252	3.9	Agree	High
Recognition	0.379	3.8	Agree	High
Career Development	0.321	3.7	Agree	High
Engagement	0.265	3.7	Agree	High
Respect	0.321	3.7	Agree	High
Overall	0.329	3.7	Agree	High

The Extent of Workplace Spirituality of Public-School Teachers

Table 3 shows the extent of workplace spirituality among public school teachers. The data gathered were treated using the mean.

Regarding compassion, the extent of workplace spirituality of public-school teachers was extensively observed all the time, with a mean score of 3.4, which indicates always. Thus, it indicates that the teachers were always aware and they sympathized with others, tried to help their coworkers relieve their suffering, and knew their coworkers' needs.

In terms of mindfulness, the extent of workplace spirituality of public-school teachers was extensive most of the time, with a mean score of 3.0, sharing that the teachers often did jobs or tasks automatically and found themselves working without paying attention, but they disagreed that they broke or spilled things because of carelessness or rushed through worked activities without being attentive to them. They also disagreed that they went to place on "automatic pilot" and then wondered why they went there or that they were working automatically without much awareness of what they were doing. They manifested a disagreement.

In terms of meaningful work, the extent of workplace spirituality of public school teachers was extensive most of the time. The mean score of 3.1 specifies that the teachers often experienced joy in their work, looked forward to coming to work in most days, believed that others experienced joy as a result of their work, and that their work energized their spirit. They also strongly agreed that they understood what gave their work personal meaning and that it was connected to what they thought was important in life.

The extent of public school teachers' workplace spirituality was extensive in transcendence, with a mean score of 3.0. Thus, it implies that the teachers often experienced moments at work where they felt the energy, vitality, and happiness and had no sense of time or space. They also strongly agreed that they had moments at work in which they experienced complete joy and ecstasy.

Table 3. The Extent of Workplace Spirituality of Public-School Teachers

Indicators	SD	Mean	Description	Interpretation
Compassion	0.18	3.4	Always	Extensively observed all the time
Mindfulness	0.39	3.0	Often	Extensive, most of the time
Meaningful Work	0.23	3.1	Often	Extensive, most of the time
Transcendence	0.18	3.0	Often	Extensive, most of the time
Overall	0.245	3.1	Often	Extensive, most of the time

Significant Relationship between Job Satisfaction and Workplace Spirituality

Table 4 shows the significant relationship between job satisfaction and workplace spirituality.

Based on the given data, there was a significant relationship between job satisfaction and workplace spirituality. The computed value of 0.77 was more significant than the tabular value of 0.159 at a significance level of 0.05. The null hypothesis was thus rejected,

suggesting that there was a meaningful connection between workplace spirituality and job happiness. It implied that those who encountered spirituality at work were likelier to report feeling more satisfied with their jobs.

Table 4. *Significant Relationship between Job Satisfaction and Workplace Spirituality*

Variables	Df	rxy value n=161		Decision a= 0.05	Analysis
		Computed	Tabular		
Job Satisfaction Vs Workplace Spirituality	159	0.77	0.159	Reject null hypothesis	There is a significant relationship

Significant Relationship between Job Satisfaction and Professional Commitment

Table 5 shows the significant relationship between job satisfaction and professional commitment.

The results presented indicated a substantial correlation between professional dedication and work happiness. The calculated value is 0.80, exceeding the zero tabular value. 159 with a degree of significance of 0.05. Consequently, the null hypothesis was rejected, suggesting that a statistically significant correlation existed between professional dedication and work satisfaction. It suggested that individuals who had a more substantial commitment to their profession were more likely to have higher levels of job satisfaction.

Table 5. *Significant Relationship between Job Satisfaction and Professional Commitment*

Variables	Df	rxy value n=161		Decision a= 0.05	Analysis
		Computed	Tabular		
Job Satisfaction Vs Professional Commitment	159	0.80	0.159	Reject null hypothesis	There is a significant relationship.

Significant Relationship between Job Satisfaction and Workplace Spirituality

Table 6 shows the significant relationship between professional commitment and workplace spirituality.

The result indicated a significant relationship between professional commitment and workplace spirituality. The computed value of 0.78 was more significant than the tabular value of 0.159 at a significance level of 0.05. As a consequence, the null hypothesis was rejected, and it was discovered that there was a significant relationship between professional devotion and workplace spirituality.

It suggested that spiritually oriented individuals are more likely to have a more substantial commitment to their profession.

Table 6. *Significant Relationship between Professional Commitment and Workplace Spirituality*

Variables	Df	rxy value n=161		Decision a= 0.05	Analysis
		Computed	Tabular		
Professional Commitment Vs Workplace Spirituality	159	0.78	0.159	Reject null hypothesis	There is a significant relationship.

The Significant Mediation of Professional Commitment on Job Satisfaction and Workplace Spirituality

Table 7 shows the significance of the mediation of professional commitment on job satisfaction and workplace spirituality.

Based on the given data, professional commitment partially mediated the relationship between job satisfaction and workplace spirituality. The standardized coefficients suggested that job satisfaction and workplace spirituality had significant direct effects on professional commitment and that professional commitment partially mediated the relationship between these variables.

The direct effect of job satisfaction on professional commitment was significant, with a standardized coefficient of 0.106. It suggested that the individuals who were more satisfied with their jobs were likelier to commit to their profession.

The standardized coefficient for the indirect effect of job satisfaction on workplace spirituality through professional commitment was

0.064, indicating a significant partial mediating effect. It suggests that job satisfaction indirectly affects workplace spirituality through its impact on professional commitment.

The direct effect of workplace spirituality on professional commitment was also significant, with a standardized coefficient of 0.612, indicating that spiritual individuals were more likely to have a more substantial commitment to their profession.

Table 7. *The Significance of Mediation of Professional Commitment on Job Satisfaction and Workplace Spirituality Mediating Effect; Path Analysis (Patial Mediation)*

PATH	ESTIMATES		SE	C.R.	P
	Unstandardized	Standardized			
Job Satisfaction → Workplace Spirituality	.878	.756	.034	28.343	***
Job Satisfaction → Professional Commitment	.185	.106	.040	2.360	.018
Workplace Spirituality → Professional Commitment	.656	.612	.044	15.700	***

Conclusions

In light of the gathered information, it is evident that there exists a robust and positive association between professional commitment, job satisfaction, and workplace spirituality. The high level of professional commitment, specifically in affective, continuance, and normative dimensions, reflects a profound dedication to one's profession. Job satisfaction was notably high, particularly in terms of pay, benefits, job security, recognition, career development, engagement, and respect. Additionally, workplace spirituality was extensively present, with a focus on compassion, mindfulness, meaningful work, and transcendence.

The study revealed a strong correlation between professional dedication and workplace spirituality, as well as between job happiness and spirituality in the workplace. While the connection between job satisfaction and workplace spirituality was significant, it was described as partial, indicating that other factors may also play a role in determining job satisfaction. These conclusions emphasize the importance of integrating professional commitment and spiritual elements in the workplace to foster a positive work environment and enhance overall well-being.

The study's result led to the formulation of the following recommendations.

To further enhance professional commitment, the Department of Education may, among other things, offer opportunities for professional development and growth within the organization, foster a supportive work environment, acknowledge the value of the profession, and hold regular surveys or focus groups to gauge employee's commitment levels and pinpoint areas in need of improvement. They may also provide fair and competitive compensation and benefits to their employees. Job security is a crucial safety need that should be addressed by offering a stable and secure employment.

Additionally, school leaders may provide opportunities for job promotion, regular feedback on performance, and opportunities to participate in team activities. This is to foster social interaction, provide employees with recognition for their accomplishments. It may emphasize the importance of teachers' work and the positive impact it has on the learners' lives, and provide opportunities for teachers to connect their works on their values and goals.

Moreover, teachers may engage in practices that may enhance mindfulness and may help them experience positive emotions and a sense of connection to their work, may focus on developing their compassion, mindfulness, and sense of meaningful work to enhance their workplace spirituality, and may practice being fully engaged in their works and pay attention to their surroundings and actions.

Finally, this study may be a starting point for further research on professional commitment, job satisfaction, and workplace spirituality among public school teachers. Future research may explore additional variables, such as the role of leadership and organizational culture, and may also assess teacher's performance and student's outcomes.

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